

MONETARY POLICY TRANSMISSION AND FINANCIAL STABILITY SYSTEM BEFORE AND DURING COVID-19 IN EMERGING MARKET COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This study aims to effectively analyze the contribution of variables to Monetary Policy Transmission and Financial Stability Before and During Covid-19 in Emerging Markets Countries. This type of research uses secondary data or time series, namely from 2010 to 2021 and monthly data from 2020 to 2021. The data analysis model in this study is the ARDL Panel model and the different test methods with SPSS 26. The results of the ARDL Panel show that on a panel basis, it turns out that the money supply can also be a leading indicator for controlling China, Russia, Brazil, Turkey, and Egypt. Still, its position is not stable in the short run. The leading indicators of the effectiveness of variables in controlling the stability of 7 emerging market countries, namely money demand and Investment, are seen from the short-run and long-run equilibrium, where the money demand variable is good in the long term and significantly in controlling economic stability. The results of the analysis of the different test methods are known that in China, only the SB variable has significant changes in the period before and during covid-19. In India and Russia, the variable that has a substantial change in the period before and during COVID-19 is the GDP variable. The country of Indonesia had significant changes in the period before and during the Covid-19 period, namely 3 SB variables, GDP, and Inflation. The last two countries are Turkey and Egypt; the variable that significantly changes the period before and during COVID-19 is GDP.

Keywords: Covid-19, Financial Stability and Monetary Policy Transmission.

I. INTRODUCTION

The maintenance of monetary stability is one of the dimensions of the strength of a country which is an integral part and target of national development (Andre et al. 1, 2021) (Auclert et al. 1 2020). Maintaining currency value stabilization is not an easy matter because the currency is related to almost all current economic activities. This reason is also able to strengthen that the monetary policy process to touch the real sector becomes a very complex problem (Coibion et al., 2020) (Coibon et al. 1, 2022) (World Bank, 2021). This process is then commonly referred to as the monetary policy transmission mechanism (MTKM), which is a channel connecting monetary policy to the real economy (Arini, 2019) (Li et al. 1, 2021) (Krieger et al. 1, 2021) (Lang et al. 1, 2021).

From the end of 2019 to 2020, there was a very severe world economic recession due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The highest number of cases was found in European countries and then in the Americas to the least in Africa (WHO, 2020). To date, many countries have established self-locking from other countries as a precautionary measure to prevent further spread (Dunford et al., 2020) (Azevedo et al. 1, 2020) (Brusseovich et al. 1, 2020).

Covid has hurt the global economy. The IMF noted that the worldwide economy had fallen

into a crisis after about 95 percent of countries were projected to experience contraction or suffer negative economic growth. In addition, the IMF noted that the coronavirus pandemic had also caused global financial losses of US\$ 12 trillion or around Rp. 168,000 trillion. Emerging markets and economies will face negative per capita income growth in 2020. Except for China, emerging markets and countries are projected to experience a bigger hit in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth than developed countries from 2020 to 2021. Thus, it is necessary to have supporting factors for macroeconomic stability to restore the world's economy.

In supporting more optimal macroeconomic stability and creating a solid and anticipatory monetary policy framework, it is necessary to have an appropriate monetary policy to achieve the long-term stability target. This means that other supporting factors besides interest rates in maintaining economic stability are very influential, as reflected in a low and stable inflation rate, one of which is the exchange rate.

Figure1: Graph of Real Interest Rate (%) Before and During Covid-19

Based on the tables and graphs above, there are very significant changes in interest rates that occurred in several selected countries. One of them is seen in Turkey. This country experienced a drastic increase in interest rates. This increase was carried out by the Central Bank of Turkey (Türkiye Cumhuriyet Merkez Bankası/TCMB) to create Turkey's economy closer to the market. Thus creating a high number of investments that can boost an even better economic growth.

However, this is different from China, the country accused of being the origin of the virus, which is troubling the world. China has cut interest rates by up to 2%. This interest rate cut was carried out by offering funds with low-interest rates; the Central Bank of China (PBoC) was able to keep interest rates on interbank loans low after previously cutting banks' statutory reserve requirements. It is hoped that the reduction in interest rates can accelerate economic activity after being hit by the coronavirus outbreak.

Figure 2: Inflation (%) Before and During Covid-19

The tables and graphs above show that there is movement in the inflation data. The country of Indonesia experienced a decrease in the inflation rate, which indicated a growth in the deflation rate in this country. Inflation in 2020 of 1.68 percent is the lowest annual inflation rate since BPS released inflation figures. This is indeed the lowest inflation rate in 2020, triggered mainly by food, beverages, and tobacco, with a share of 0.19 percent. But apart from that, other things caused this to happen; on the other hand, several groups contributed to deflation, namely transportation with a share of minus 0.11 percent and a deflation rate of minus 0.85 percent, as well as the information, communication, and financial services group. With a share of minus 0.02 percent and a deflation rate of minus 0.35 percent.

II. METHODOLOGY

Refresh Panel ARDL (Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag)

This technique examines each lag variable located at I(1) or I(0). On the other hand, the ARDL regression result is a test statistic compared with two asymptotic critical values.

ARDL Panel Testing with the formula:

$$INF_{it-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 EKS_{it} + \beta_4 JUB_{it} + \beta_5 INV_{it} + \beta_6 KURS_{it} + \epsilon$$

The following is the ARDL panel formula for several countries:

$$INF_{CHINA\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

$$INF_{INDIA\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

$$INF_{RUSSIA\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

$$INF_{INDONESIA\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

$$INF_{BRAZIL\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

$$INF_{TURKEY\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

$$INF_{MESIR\ t-p} = \alpha + \beta_1 SB_{it} + \beta_2 PDB_{it} + \beta_3 KURS_{it} + \beta_4 Eks_{it} + \beta_5 JUB_{it} + \beta_6 INV_{it} + \beta_7 INF_{it} + \epsilon$$

Information:

- INF : inflation (%)
- SB : world central bank interest rates (%)
- INV : investment (US\$)
- PDB : gross domestic product (%)
- Kurs : The exchange rate of the rupiah against the US dollar (IDR)
- JUB : Total Money Supply (%)
- EX : Export (US\$)
- € : error term
- β : regression coefficient
- α : constant
- i : number of observations (5 countries)
- t : the amount of time (9 years, 2010 to 2018)

Test Different Test:

Independent Sample T-Test was used to test the significance of the difference in the mean of the two groups. This test is also used to test the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. To examine the significant differences in Inflation, interest rates, and

exchange rates before and during covid-19-19 in Emerging Markets Countries. The basis for deciding to accept or reject H_0 in this test is as follows.

- a. H_0 is rejected, and H_a is accepted if $\text{sig (2-tailed)} = 0.05$, where there is a significant difference in the variables before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.
- b. H_0 is accepted, and H_a is rejected if $\text{sig (2-tailed)} = 0.05$, where there is no significant difference in the variables before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.

III. DISCUSSION

ARDL Panel Test Results

Table 1.1 Results of ARDL Panel Indicator Leading

Variable	CHINA	INDIA	RUSIA	INDO NESIA	BRAZIL	TURK EY	EGYP T	Short Run	Long Run
Interest rate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
GDP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Exchange Rate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Export	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
JUB	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1
Investment	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1

Source: E views output results, 2022

The main recommendations of government effectiveness in controlling the stability of 7 emerging market countries, namely China, Russia, Brazil, Turkey, and Egypt, in controlling Inflation are carried out by JUB. While India and Indonesia are still under-invested, their position is unstable in the short and long term, whereas the JUB variable controls economic stability for a long time.

Monetary policy with an economic magnitude price approach can have a practical effect on controlling Inflation through interest rate and exchange rate channels (Nguyen, 2015) (Almeida et al. 1, 2021) (Baker et al. 1, 2020) (Brewer et al. 1, 2021). The increase in JUB can also increase GDP because the public consumption level directly adds to economic growth. On the other hand, if there is a decrease in the JUB, then GDP will also experience a decline because the decline in JUB in productivity will cause the economy to reduce the production of goods and services.

Test Different Test:

Table 1.2. Test Results Independent Sample T-Test

Country	Results Sig. (2 - tailed Paired Samples Test)		
	SB_before_COVID SB_after_COVID	PDB_before_COVID PDB_after_COVID	INF_before_COVID INF_after_COVID
China	.001	.742	.942
India	.058	.007	.057
Russian	.087	.013	.098
Indonesia	.037	.013	.008
Brazil	.042	.003	.019
Turkey	.062	.023	.099
Mesir	.077	.038	.407

Source: SPSS. Output, 2022

In China, only the SB variable has a significant change in the period before and during covid-19. Loose monetary policy usually results in higher Inflation. China's inflation rate has increased along with the increase in pork prices. The country faces a significant shortage in staple food caused by the outbreak of African swine fever on Chinese pig farms last year. In September, pork prices jumped 69.3% from a year ago (Reuters, 2020).

India and Russia have a variable that has a significant change in the period before and during covid-19, namely the GDP variable. The reason is that the pandemic did not occur amid unequal macroeconomic conditions and the financial system of the four countries. Macro policy-making's massive scale and speed are also considered a savior of their situation (Oktaveri, 2020).

The countries of Indonesia and Brazil that had significant changes before and during the COVID-19 were three variables SB, GDP, and Inflation. These two countries have movements in external variables that can continue to experience increasing fluctuations during the covid-19 pandemic. Brazil The deficit in 2020 widened and approached 500 billion Brazilian rials or the equivalent of US\$ 96 billion. This position is 7% of Brazil's gross domestic product (GDP), even before the proposal for state aid of up to 222 billion Brazilian rials to deal with the coronavirus is taken into account (Hasan, 2020).

In Turkey and Egypt, the variable that has a significant change in the period before and during COVID-19 is GDP. These two countries are the wealthiest Muslim countries globally, with the top 10. Turkey is also a country as the 15th largest GDP contributor globally. The country's GDP increased 4.5% in the first quarter of this year and 0.9% in 2019. Before the new coronavirus crisis, the economy was forecast to grow 5% in 2020, as stated in the country's current economic program announced last September (Syafira, 2020).

IV. CONCLUSION

Main Recommendations Variable Performance in Managing Stability 7 Emerging Markets, namely JUB and Investments (China, India, Russia, Indonesia, Brazil, Turkey, and Egypt), short-term and long-term stability. Where the JUB variable is good in the long run, controlling for economic stability significantly

In China, only the SB variable has a significant change in the period before and during covid-19. India and Russia have variables that have significant changes in the period before and during covid-19, namely the GDP variable. Then for the State of Indonesia, which had significant differences before and during covid-19, namely 3 SB variables, GDP, and Inflation. Then for the last two countries, Turkey and Egypt, the variable that significantly changed in the period before and during COVID-19 was GDP.

REFERENCES

- 1) Almeida, V., S. Barrios, M. Christl, S. De Poli, A. Tumino, and W. van der Wielen. 2021. "The Impact of COVID-19 on Households' Income in the EU." *Journal of Economic Inequality* 19; 413-31
- 2) Andre, P., Pizzinelli, C., Roth, C., Wohlfart, J., 2021. Subjective models of the macroeconomy: evidence from experts and representative samples. *Review of Economic Studies*. Forthcoming.
- 3) Arini. (2019). Guncangan Indikator Makro Terhadap Transmisi Kebijakan Moneter Pada Jalur Nilai Tukar . *Elastisitas Jurnal Ekonomi Pembangunan*.
- 4) Auclert, A., Rognlie, M., Straub, L., 2020. Micro Jumps, Macro Humps: Monetary Policy and Business Cycles in an Estimated HANK Model. Working Paper. National Bureau of Economic Research. 26647 DOI: 10.3386/w26647.
- 5) Azevedo, J. P., A. Hasan, D. Goldemberg, S. A. Iqbal, and K. Geven. 2020. "Simulating the Potential Impacts of the COVID-19 School Closures on Schooling and Learning Outcomes: A Set of Global Estimates." *Policy Research Working Paper 9284*, World Bank, Washington, DC.
- 6) Baker, S. R., R. A. Farrokhnia, S. Meyer, M. Pagel, and C. Yannelis. 2020a. "How Does Household Spending Respond to an Epidemic? Consumption during the 2020 COVID-19 Pandemic." *NBER Working Paper 26949*, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge, MA.
- 7) Brewer, M. and I. V. Tassel. 2021. "Did the UK Policy Response to Covid-19 Protect Household Incomes?" *Journal of Economic Inequality* 19: 433-58.
- 8) Brussevich, M., E. Dabla-Norris, and S. Khalid. 2020. "Who will bear the Brunt of Lockdown Policies? Evidence from Tele-workability Measures across Countries." *IMF Working Paper 20/88*, International Monetary Fund, Washington, DC.
- 9) Coibion, O., Gorodnichenko, Y., Weber, M., 2020. The Cost of the Covid-19 Crisis: Lockdowns, Macroeconomic Expectations, and Consumer Spending. Working Paper. National Bureau of Economic Research. 27141 DOI: 10.3386/w27141.
- 10) Coibion, O., Gorodnichenko, Y., Weber, M., 2022. Monetary Policy Communications and their Effects on Household Inflation Expectations. *Journal of Political Economy*, forthcoming.
- 11) Dunford, D., Dale, B., Stylianou, N., Lowther, E., Ahmed, M., & Arenas, I. d. I. T. (2020). Coronavirus: The World in Lockdown in Maps and Charts. *Bbc.com*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-52103747>.
- 12) Hasibuan, S. (2014). Mekanisme Transmisi Kebijakan Moneter Melalui Suku Bunga Sbi. *Jurnal Ekonomi*

dan Keuangan.

- 13) Julius R. Latumaerissa, Bank dan Lembaga Keuangan Lain, Salemba Empat, Jakarta, 2012.
- 14) Krieger, K., Mauck, N., Pruitt, S.W., 2021. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on dividends. Finance. Res. Lett. 42 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2020.101910>.
- 15) Lang, S., Schrader, W., 2021. The trilemma of expansionary monetary policy in the Euro area during the COVID-19 crisis. Finance. Res. Lett. 42, 102048 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FRL.2021.102048>.
- 16) Li, Y., Mu, Y., Qin, T., 2021b. Economic uncertainty: a pivotal factor to understanding personal volatility puzzle. Finance. Res. Lett. 42 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2021.101938>
- 17) M.Hasan. (2020). Pembanguna Ekonomi . Eprint.Unm.
- 18) Mishkin, F.S, 2004. The Economics of Money, Banking and Financial Markets. Seventh Edition. International Edition, New York: Pearson Addison Wesley Longman.
- 19) Nguyen, T. (2015). The Effectiveness of Online Learning : Beyond No Significant Difference and Future Horizons. Journal of Online Learning and Teaching.
- 20) Novella, S. (2017). Pengaruh Sektor Moneter terhadap Penguatan Stabilitas Sistem Keuangan di Indonesia. repository.trisakti.
- 21) Oktaveri, J. A. (2020). Krisis Covid-19, India Gelontorkan Paket Stimulus Ekonmi Us\$27 Miliar. Jakarta: Bisnis.Com.
- 22) Reuters, C. (2020). China Tak Pangkas Suku Bunga Seperti Negara Lain, Salah Satu Alasannya Karena Babi. International.Kontan.Co.Id.
- 23) Rusiadi, dkk. (2014). Metode Penelitian. Medan: USU Press.
- 24) Syafira. (2020). Ini Keadaan Ekonomi Turki Akibat Covid-19. Jakarta: Katakini.Com.
- 25) Taylor, John B. (2009), the Financial Crisis and Monetary Response: An Empirical Analysis of What Went Wrong, NBER Working Paper Series No. 14631.
- 26) World Bank, 2021. Global Economics Prospects. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt183pb3w.5>.